

Development and Synthesis of New Zeolite Nanocomposite Adsorbent CuO/ZnFe₂O₄/NaA for Inactivation of New Drug Sarin Simulator

Pourya Zarshenas¹; Meysam Sadeghi^{2*}; Mohammad Mahmoudi Alemi³

¹Faculty of Chemistry and Petroleum Sciences, Shahid Beheshti University (SBU), Iran.

²Department of Chemistry, Lorestan University, Khorramabad, Iran.

³Department of Chemistry, Golestan University, Gorgan, Iran.

*Corresponding Author(s): Meysam Sadeghi

Department of Chemistry, Lorestan University,
Khorramabad, Iran.

E-mail: meysamsadeghi1364@gmail.com

Abstract

The aim of present research is to evaluate the decontamination of nerve agent sarin simulant Dimethyl Methyl Phosphonate (DMMP) in water media using the CuO/ZnFe₂O₄/NaA zeolite as a novel ternary nanocomposite adsorbent. In this regard, the CuO and ZnFe₂O₄ nanoparticles were successfully synthesized within the NaA zeolite applying the ultrasound-assisted hydrothermal route and characterized via XRD, FESEM, FTIR, EDAX, VSM and BET analyses. Then, the CuO/ZnFe₂O₄/NaA nanocomposite activity was investigated for the decontamination of DMMP molecule and monitored by a GC-FID and GC-MS analyses. Plus, the impacts of several parameters, including contact time, adsorbent dose and adsorbent type on the decontamination of DMMP were studied. The gained data from GC-FID analysis confirmed the maximum decontamination more than 98.4% for DMMP. The parameters including: adsorbent amount of 50 mg and contact time of 40 min were achieved as the optimized values for the decontamination reaction. In addition, the non-toxic Methyl Phosphoric Acid (MPA) as the DMMP degradation product in the presence of CuO/ZnFe₂O₄/NaA adsorbent was characterized.

Received: Dec 15, 2021

Accepted: Jan 27, 2022

Published Online: Jan 31, 2022

Journal: Journal of Nanomedicine

Publisher: MedDocs Publishers LLC

Online edition: <http://meddocsonline.org/>

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Keywords: CuO/ZnFe₂O₄/NaA; Zeolite; Nerve agent sarin simulant; Decontamination; Dimethyl Methyl phosphonate (DMMP); Methyl Phosphoric Acid (MPA).

Introduction

Today, organic dye sewages are a main source of water contamination [1,2]. Every year, the estimation demonstrates that up to 15% of dye sewages are evacuated into the surface and ground water supplies [3,4]. The exposure with these dye contaminants even at very low concentrations can be harmful to human and the environment [5]. For this reason, these toxic compounds must be removed from the environment. Recently, the various beneficial methodologies like adsorption, mem-

brane filtration, electrochemical treatment, oxidation, ozonation, photocatalytic and sonocatalytic processes have been implemented for the removal of toxic organic dyes in the polluted aqueous solutions [6-11]. Among the aforementioned methods, the sonochemical process is considered as an effective route for the removal of these types of organic pollutants [12]. Plus, applying the ultrasound irradiation causes the production of the bubbles inside the reaction solution leading to the formation of high pressure and temperature approximately

Cite this article: Zarshenas P, Sadeghi M, Alemi MM. Development and Synthesis of New Zeolite Nanocomposite Adsorbent CuO/ZnFe₂O₄/NaA for Inactivation of New Drug Sarin Simulator. J Nanomed. 2022; 5(1): 1049.

1000 atm and 5000 K, respectively and subsequently the production of hot spots [13,14]. Eventually, the produced hot spots can in turn lead to the Hydroxyl Radical ($\cdot\text{OH}$) and superoxide Anion Radical ($\cdot\text{O}_2^-$) originated from the breakdown of H_2O and O_2 molecules, respectively. Furthermore, it has been specified that the use of semiconductor catalysts along with the US/ H_2O_2 system provide higher degradation performance in comparison to the H_2O_2 only and US only. Additionally, different types of catalysts, involving Cr-MIL-101@NiO/13X, $\text{InVO}_4/\text{TiO}_2$, $\text{NiGa}_2\text{O}_4/\text{CeO}_2$, $\text{CoFe}_2\text{O}_4/\text{CdS}$, $\text{La}/\text{TiO}_2/\text{Y}$ have been used for the removal of organic dye pollutants via the sonodegradation processes [15-19]. Among these types of reported catalysts, Metal-Organic Frameworks (MOFs) and Zeolites are considered as new classes of porous compounds that have various applications due to their different properties such as catalysis, nanofluids, chemical sensing and so on [20-22]. On the other hand, the zeolites are introduced as a group of hydrated crystalline aluminosilicate involving alkali and alkaline earth metals [23]. These materials possess unique properties such as high hydrothermal stabil-

ity and biocompatibility, large pore volume and high surface area, which is suitable for its use as catalysis, adsorbents and so on [24-26]. Regarding the aforementioned explanations, it is explicitly known that combining the ZnFe_2O_4 nanoparticles with CuO in the NaA zeolite framework will produce a magnetically separable and superior nanocomposite catalyst that remarkably facilitates the hole and electron separation. Hence, in the presence work, the $\text{CuO}/\text{ZnFe}_2\text{O}_4/\text{NaA}$, nanocomposite sonocatalyst was prepared using the ultrasound assisted-hydrothermal route. The as-prepared nanocomposite was fully characterized via the FESEM, EDAX, FTIR, XRD and BET analyses. Then, the above-mentioned nanocomposite catalyst was assessed for the effective sonodegradation of MB dye from aqueous solution in the presence of the Ultrasound (US)/ H_2O_2 system. Besides, the impacts of several parameters like contact time, H_2O_2 concentration, initial MB concentration and sonocatalyst dosage on the MB degradation were studied. Nevertheless, as far as we know, no study has been done on the sonodegradation reaction in the presence of the $\text{CuO}/\text{ZnFe}_2\text{O}_4/\text{NaA}/\text{US}/\text{H}_2\text{O}_2$ system in before.

Figure 1: Graphical abstract: Photocatalytic Activity of $\text{ZnO}/\text{CuO}/\text{ZnFe}_2\text{O}_4$ Nanocomposite [28].

Conclusion

In this research, the ultrasound-assisted hydrothermal method was used to fabricate magnetic $\text{CuO}/\text{ZnFe}_2\text{O}_4/\text{NaA}$ zeolite as a novel nanocomposite. The noteworthy activity of the $\text{CuO}/\text{ZnFe}_2\text{O}_4/\text{NaA}$ nanocomposite for the decontamination of DMMP in aqueous solution was investigated and monitored via GC-FID analysis. Besides, the influences of several parameters such as contact time, adsorbent amount and adsorbent type on the decontamination efficiency of DMMP were evaluated. On the basis of the GC-FID analysis outcomes, the decontamination (98.4%) of DMMP in the presence of the $\text{CuO}/\text{ZnFe}_2\text{O}_4/\text{NaA}$ under the optimized conditions of contact time 40 min and adsorbent amount of 50 mg was proved. Alternatively, the high activity of above-mentioned nanocomposite makes it a superior candidate to utilize in the decontamination applications of chemical warfare agents [27].

References

1. Karla Aparecida Guimarães Gusmão, Leandro Vinícius Alves Gurgel, Tânia Márcia Sacramento Melo, Laurent Frédéric Gil. "Adsorption studies of methylene blue and gentian violet on sugarcane bagasse modified with EDTA Dianhydride (EDTAD) in aqueous solutions: kinetic and equilibrium aspects." *Journal of environmental management*. 2013; 118: 135-143.

Figure 2: SEM of the: A) ZnFe_2O_4 ; B) CuO ; C,D) $\text{ZnFe}_2\text{O}_4\text{-CuO}$.

2. Asma Turki, Chantal Guillard, Frederic Dappozze, Z Ksibi, Gilles Berhault, et al. "Phenol photocatalytic degradation over anisotropic TiO_2 nanomaterials: Kinetic study, adsorption isotherms and formal mechanisms." *Applied Catalysis B: Environmental*. 2015; 163: 404-414.
3. Harpreet Singh Rai, Mani Shankar Bhattacharyya, Jagdeep Singh, Tk Bansal, Purva Vats, et al. "Removal of dyes from the effluent of textile and dyestuff manufacturing industry: a review of emerging techniques with reference to biological treatment." *Critical reviews in environmental science and technology*. 2005; 35: 219-238.
4. Gupta VK. "Application of low-cost adsorbents for dye removal—a review." *Journal of environmental management*. 2009; 90: 2313-2342.
5. Sadettin Sevgil and Gönül Dönmez. "Bioaccumulation of reactive dyes by thermophilic cyanobacteria." *Process Biochemistry*. 2006; 41: 836-841.
6. Behnajady MA, N Modirshahla, S Bavili Tabrizi, S Molanee. "Ultrasound degradation of Rhodamine B in aqueous solution: Influence of operational parameters." *Journal of Hazardous Materials*. 2008; 152: 381-386.
7. Zhang DQ, WL Zhang and YN Liang. "Adsorption of perfluoroalkyl and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFASs) from aqueous solution-A

- review." *Science of the Total Environment*. 2019; 694: 133606.
8. Qin Yalin, Beihui Tan and Baoxue Zhou. "RhB adsorption performance of magnetic adsorbent Fe₃O₄/RGO composite and its regeneration through a fenton-like reaction." *Nano-Micro Letters*. 2014; 6: 125-135.
 9. Sboui M, Nsib MF, Rayes A, Swaminathan M, Houas A. "TiO₂-PANI/Cork composite: A new floating photocatalyst for the treatment of organic pollutants under sunlight irradiation." *Journal of Environmental Sciences*. 2017; 60: 3-13.
 10. Ayyappan Carmalin Sophia, VM Bhalambaal, Sunil Kumar. "Effect of biochar on bio-electrochemical dye degradation and energy production." *Bioresource technology*. 2018; 251: 165-170.
 11. MA El Hajj Hassan and MM El Jamal. Kinetic Study of the Electrochemical Oxidation of Methylene Blue with Pt Electrode. *Port. Electrochimica Acta*. 2012; 30: 351-359.
 12. Ghodbane, Houria and Oualid Hamdaoui. "Degradation of Acid Blue 25 in aqueous media using 1700 kHz ultrasonic irradiation: Ultrasound/Fe (II) and ultrasound/H₂O₂ combinations." *Ultrasonics Sonochemistry*. 2009; 16: 593-598.
 13. Mason Timothy J, J. Phillip Lorimer. *Applied sonochemistry: the uses of power ultrasound in chemistry and processing*. Weinheim: Wiley-Vch. 2002; 10.
 14. Rajoriya Sunil, Swapnil Bargole and Virendra Kumar Saharan. "Degradation of reactive blue 13 using hydrodynamic cavitation: Effect of geometrical parameters and different oxidizing additives." *Ultrasonics sonochemistry*. 2017; 37: 192-202.
 15. Sadeghi, Meysam, Zabardasti, Abedien, Farhadi, et al. "Immobilization of Cr-MIL-101 over the NiO/13X zeolite nanocomposite towards ultrasound-assisted destruction of organic dyes in aqueous media." *Journal of Water Process Engineering*. 2019; 32: 100946.
 16. YuLin Min, KanZhang, YouCunChen, YuanGuangZhang. "Sono-degradation and photodegradation of methyl orange by InVO₄/TiO₂ nanojunction composites under ultrasonic and visible light irradiation." *Ultrasonics sonochemistry*. 2012; 19: 883-889.
 17. Guowei Wang, Xue Ma, Jue Liu, Lifan Qin, Bing Li, et al. "Design and performance of a novel direct Z-scheme NiGa₂O₄/CeO₂ nanocomposite with enhanced sonocatalytic activity." *Science of the Total Environment*. 2020; 741: 140192.
 18. Atheel Hassan Alwash, Ahmad Zuhairi Abdullah and Norli Ismail. "La loaded TiO₂ encapsulated zeolite Y catalysts: Investigating the characterization and decolorization process of amaranth dye." *Journal of Engineering* 2013.
 19. Farhadi Saeed, and Firouzeh Siadatnasab. "CoFe₂O₄/CdS nanocomposite: Preparation, characterisation, and application in sonocatalytic degradation of organic dye pollutants." *Chinese Journal of Catalysis*. 2016; 37: 1487-1495.
 20. Sadeghi Meysam, et al. "Immobilization of Cr-MIL-101 over the NiO/13X zeolite nanocomposite towards ultrasound-assisted destruction of organic dyes in aqueous media." *Journal of Water Process Engineering*. 2019; 32: 100946.
 21. Mariana L Díaz-Ramírez, Elí Sánchez-González, J Raziel Álvarez, Gerardo A González-Martínez, Satoshi Horike, et al. "Partially fluorinated MIL-101 (Cr): from a miniscule structure modification to a huge chemical environment transformation inspected by 129 Xe NMR." *Journal of Materials Chemistry A*. 2019; 7: 15101-15112.
 22. Sadeghi Meysam, Saeed Farhadi, and Abedin Zabardasti. "A novel CoFe₂O₄@ Cr-MIL-101/Y zeolite ternary nanocomposite as a magnetically separable sonocatalyst for efficient sonodegradation of organic dye contaminants from water." *RSC Advances*. 2020; 10: 10082-10096.
 23. Sadeghi Meysam, et al. "MnO₂ NPs-AgX zeolite composite as adsorbent for removal of strontium-90 (90Sr) from water samples: Kinetics and thermodynamic reactions study." *Materials Chemistry and Physics*. 2017; 197: 113-122.
 24. Dehghani Modarres, Azadeh Tadjarodi, and Sanaz Chamani. "Synthesis and Characterization of Magnetic Zeolite Y-Palladium-Nickel Ferrite by Ultrasonic Irradiation and Investigating Its Catalytic Activity in Suzuki-Miyaura Cross-Coupling Reactions." *ACS omega*. 2019; 4: 10640-10648.
 25. Meysam Sadeghi, Sina Yekta, Daryoush Mirzaei, Abedin Zabardasti, Saeid Farhadi. "Synthesis of novel MnCo₂O₄/NaY zeolite nanocomposite adsorbent and its performance for Sr²⁺ ions removal from drinking water." *Journal of Inclusion Phenomena and Macroscopic Chemistry*. 2019; 93: 215-227.
 26. Ramezani Hamed, Seyed Naser Azizi and Sayed Reza Hosseini. "NaY zeolite as a platform for preparation of Ag nanoparticles arrays in order to construction of H₂O₂ sensor." *Sensors and Actuators B: Chemical*. 2017; 248: 571-579.
 27. Mohammad Hossein Ghanbari, Parastoo Sharafi, Sepideh Nayeboosadr, Zahra Norouzi. "Utilizing a nanocomposite consisting of zinc ferrite, copper oxide, and gold nanoparticles in the fabrication of a metformin electrochemical sensor supported on a glassy carbon electrode." *Microchimica Acta*. 2020; 187: 1-11.
 28. Li Zhenzhen, Huabin Chen and Wenxia Liu. "Full-spectrum photocatalytic activity of ZnO/CuO/ZnFe₂O₄ nanocomposite as a PhotoFenton-like catalyst." *Catalysts*. 2018; 8: 557.